

8T – Ripping Apart Space-Time

"Some great new ideas are required." Richard Feynman.

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series, it is possible to construct a situation in which by generating energies larger than the first element in the coupling series, space will be ripped apart. That is by splitting the net curvature of the first coupling term to a composite elements, non-integers which are not isomorphic to any particle. than space-time can re-create itself as those composite be re-united to create the original element. Nature does not impose any restriction on those elements.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. Suppose that instead of the original representation of the original coupling series, we would vary it. We could take the Boson of the first interaction and split it, to any number of sub- elements.

$$8 + \sum_{i=1}^K \left(\frac{1}{N_i}\right) \quad (1.4.A)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^K \left(\frac{1}{N_i}\right) = 1$$

However, in physics, the coupling constants as presented in the 8T, exist in the form:

$$\alpha^s: \alpha^w: \alpha^{-1} \rightarrow 1: 30; 128$$

So if we split the strong into sub elements we have created in a sense magnitude which are of the order:

$$\left(\frac{1}{N_i}\right)^{-1} \rightarrow N_i \quad (1.4.B)$$

In addition, from here:

$$N_i \gg 1$$

Since those magnitudes implies Bosons stronger than the strong interaction, which do not exist or else would have been easily detected, by their effects, those fractions can not be associated with a Bosonic particle. Those fractions however are not forbidden by nature as long as they can rejoin to the formation of the original net variation, which is one. If one intuition is correct in that case, that means that space can be ripped apart at high energies, and can re-merge to original formation. That is because nature does not forbid splitting the net variation element of the strong interaction to any amount of sub elements, which correspond to much higher strength in physical meaning, which can't be a Boson. If space-time can bend, and the strongest bend is isomorphic to the strong interaction, which is one, by splitting this element and using the relation of (1.4.B) we have created higher energies which can not be isomorphic to a Boson. We thus created such an immense of curvature which is diverging outward, that space time itself could be ripped apart for some summation of N_i . Suppose that there is a limit on this parameter, space time has been ripped apart, that ripping apart means highest amount of energy, $\partial g / \partial t = 0$, since all the manifolds in the packet share that condition, which we required by the main equation, $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ means we have reached the kernel, and we can jump from manifold to manifold. If one intuition is correct $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ is the space in between two distinct manifolds flattening each other. It also means that at extremum low energies, space-time would be ripped apart to allow a gate to this space. Such a construction allow us to reason the physical phenomena of "light balls". Since the manifold is actually a flat surface getting flatter and flatter, so does this space must appear flat, and not varying over time, as $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ means does not vary overtime. So suppose some traveler would like to travel to another point on another manifold, assuming that long enough travel would get him there, he decides to travel to a radius R , $R \rightarrow \infty$ and but that is only because he does not understand that those manifolds are very close. A more knowledgeable traveler decides to use high energy or a natural light ball to reach the kernel, at a distance of $(1/R)$ from him, he gets in and within no time, he is at the point of another distinct manifold. It does not have to the inverse of R but the idea was to demonstrate that idea of distance does not apply within that space. It is currently unclear whether it is possible to jump from one point to another on the same manifold. If there exist two areas are extremum curvature are existing on the same manifold, it means that it is possible to jump from one to another again by changing to the kernel, which is the same for all. These ideas are so against intuition and hard to grasp as we are used to think in terms of linearity as means of reaching from one point to another.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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